

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART XV.
EFFECT OF NON-ELECTROLYTES

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The effect of several non-electrolytes on the stability of As_2S_3 sol has been studied.

In previous communications (this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 109; 1949, 26, 73) the effect of non-electrolytes such as methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, agar-agar, gelatin, glycol, acetone, etc. was studied with a view to finding out the variation in the coagulation concentration and the adsorption of oppositely charged ions by the colloidal particles of As_2S_3 sol by their addition.

In the present paper the work has been extended to several other non-electrolytes, namely, *n*-amyl alcohol, *iso*amyl alcohol, ethylmethyl ketone, diethyl ketone, paraldehyde, acetoacetic ester, methyl acetate and ethyl acetate in order to find out their effect on the stability of As_2S_3 sol.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure followed here is the same as given in part I (*loc. cit.*). The results obtained are given in Tables I to IX.

TABLE IA

Conc. of sol = 10.36g./litre. Sol taken = 5 c.c. Total vol. = 10 c.c. Time of coagulation = 1 hour.

Diethyl ketone (4%) added.	Coagulation conc. of N/20-BaCl ₂ .
0.0 c.c.	*0.3 c.c.
0.5	0.35
1.0	0.4
1.5	0.45
2.0	0.5

TABLE IB

Conc. of sol = 11.40g./litre. Sol taken = 5 c.c. Total vol. = 10 c.c. Time of coagulation = 1 hour.

Ethylmethyl ketone (4%) added.	Coagulation conc. of N/20-BaCl ₂ .
0.0 c.c.	0.3 c.c.
0.5	0.35
1.0	0.4
2.0	0.45
2.5	0.5

From the above table a stabilisation is observed with diethyl ketone and ethylmethyl ketone.

In the following table the adsorption of oppositely charged ions by the particles of As_2S_3 sol, when the above mentioned non-electrolytes are added in varying concentrations, are given.

TABLE II

Variation in the adsorption of Ba ions by the particles of As_2S_3 sol, when diethyl ketone (4%) added in increasing conc.

Conc. of sol = 10.36 g./litre. Radius of particles = 44μ (by extrapolation). Sol taken = 200 c.c. Total vol. = 400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken = 1.634×10^{18} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba ions.			Charge e. s. u. $\times 10^8$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	12.0 c.c.	0.0570 g.	0.0374	0.0196	6.948
Sol + 26 c.c. ketone + water	14.0	0.0598	0.0398	0.0200	7.090
Sol + 50 c.c. " + "	16.0	0.0726	0.0454	0.0272	9.642
Sol + 75 c.c. " + "	18.0	0.0743	0.0479	0.0264	8.359
Sol + 100 c.c. " + "	20.0	0.0747	0.0463	0.0284	10.070

TABLE III

Variation of adsorption of Ba ions by the particles of As₂S₃ sol, when n-amyl alcohol (2%) added in increasing conc.

Conc. of sol = 23.16 g./litre. Radius of particles = 51 $\mu\mu$ (by extrapolation).
Sol taken = 200 c.c. Total vol. = 400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken = 2.391×10^{18} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba ions.			Charge e. s. u. $\times 10^6$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	12.0 c.c.	0.0490 g.	0.0352	0.0138	2.430
Sol + 20 c.c. alcohol + water	12.8	0.0497	0.0357	0.0140	2.450
Sol + 40 c.c. .. + ..	14.0	0.0590	0.0414	0.0176	3.090
Sol + 80 c.c. .. + ..	16.0	0.0742	0.0498	0.0244	4.250
Sol + 120 c.c. .. + ..	18.0	0.0787	0.0547	0.0240	4.250

TABLE IV

Variation of adsorption of Ba ions by the particles of As₂S₃ sol, when methylethyl ketone (4%) added in increasing conc.

Conc. of sol = 11.40 g./litre. Radius of particles = 45.5 $\mu\mu$ (by extrapolation).
Sol taken = 200 c.c. Total vol. = 400 c.c. No. of particles in sol taken = 1.733×10^{18} .

Nature of sol,	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba ions.			Charge e. s. u. $\times 10^6$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	12.0 c.c.	0.0526	0.0362	0.0164	3.894
Sol + 20 c.c. ketone + water	14.0	0.0546	0.0354	0.0192	4.559
Sol + 40 + ..	16.0	0.0534	0.0338	0.0196	4.654
Sol + 80 + ..	18.0	0.0543	0.0311	0.0232	5.509
Sol + 120 + ..	20.0	0.0563	0.0343	0.0220	5.224

TABLE V

Variation in the adsorption of Ba ions by the particles of As₂S₃ sol, when isoamyl alcohol (2%) added in increasing conc.

Conc. of sol = 18.44 g./litre. Radius of particles = 48 $\mu\mu$ (by extrapolation).
Sol taken = 200 c.c. Total vol. = 400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken = 2.242×10^{18} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba ions.			Charge e. s. u. $\times 10^6$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	12.0 c.c.	0.0594	0.0222	0.0372	6.9850
Sol + 25 c.c. alcohol + water	14.0	0.0642	0.0262	0.0380	6.4960
Sol + 50 .. + ..	16.0	0.0722	0.0378	0.0344	6.4960
Sol + 75 .. + ..	17.0	0.0810	0.0390	0.0420	7.6835
Sol + 100 .. + ..	18.0	0.0763	0.0361	0.0400	7.5438

TABLE VI

Variation in the adsorption of Ba ions by the particles of As₂S₃ sol, when paraaldehyde added in increasing conc.

Conc. of sol = 18.56 g./litre. Radius of particles = 48 μ (by extrapolation). Sol taken = 200 c.c. Total vol. = 400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken = 2.25×10^{18} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba ions.			Charge e. s. u. $\times 10^8$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol. + water	12.0 c.c.	0.0562 g.	0.0366	0.0196	3.789
Sol + 12 c.c. aldehyde + water	18.0	0.0515	0.0403	0.0112	2.150
Sol + 20 .. + ..	20.0	0.0467	0.0365	0.0102	2.100
Sol + 32 .. + ..	26.0	0.0484	0.0344	0.0140	2.500
Sol + 40 .. + ..	28.0	0.0492	0.0356	0.0136	2.500

TABLE VII

Variation of adsorption of Ba ions by the particles of As₂S₃ sol, when acetoacetic ester (4%) added in increasing conc.

Conc. of the sol = 14.96 g./litre. Radius of the particles = 45 μ . (by extrapolation). Sol taken = 200 c.c. Total vol. = 400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken = 2.2×10^{18} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba ions.			Charge e. s. u. $\times 10^8$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water.	10.0 c.c.	0.0358	0.0226	0.0132	2.526
Sol + 40 c.c. ester + water	12.0	0.0490	0.0306	0.0184	3.494
Sol + 60 .. + ..	14.0	0.0590	0.0430	0.0160	3.157
Sol + 100 .. + ..	16.0	0.0522	0.0370	0.0152	2.947

TABLE VIII

Variation in the adsorption of Ba ions by the particles of As₂S₃ sol, when ethyl acetate (6%) added in increasing conc.

Conc. of sol = 14.96 g./litre. Radius of particles = 45 μ (by extrapolation). Sol taken = 200 c.c. Total vol. = 400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken = 1.208×10^{18} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba ions.			Charge e. s. u. $\times 10^8$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	10.0 c.c.	0.0578	0.0410	0.0168	5.890
Sol + 60 c.c. acetate + water	12.0	0.0626	0.0434	0.0192	6.736
Sol + 80 .. + ..	14.0	0.0618	0.0410	0.0208	7.150
Sol + 100 .. + ..	16.0	0.0558	0.0354	0.0204	7.150
Sol + 120 .. + ..	18.0	0.0592	0.0378	0.0214	7.180

TABLE IX

Variation in the adsorption of Ba ions by the particles of As_2S_3 sol, when methyl acetate (6%) added in increasing conc.

Conc. of sol = 20.32 g./litre. Radius of particles = 49μ . Sol taken = 200 c.c.
Total vol. = 400 c. c. No of particles taken = 1.322×10^{18} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba ions.			Charge e. s. u. $\times 10^7$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	10.0 c.c.	0.0502	0.0350	0.0152	5.050
Sol + 20 c.c. acetate + water	12.0	0.0586	0.0394	0.0192	5.894
Sol + 40 " + "	14.0	0.0592	0.0396	0.0196	5.890
Sol + 80 " + "	16.0	0.0614	0.0412	0.0202	6.300
Sol + 120 " + "	20.0	0.0622	0.0410	0.0212	6.400

DISCUSSION

The effect of dielectric constant and interfacial tension when non-electrolytes are added to a hydrophobic colloid has been discussed by Mukherjee and Choudhury (this *Journal*, 1925, 2, 307). It has also been pointed out by Freundlich ("Kapillar Chemie", p. 637, 1922) that a non-electrolyte diminishes the dielectric constant of the medium (*i.e.* water) when added to it and hence the charge on the colloid diminishes, or in other words, it is sensitised and so smaller amount of precipitating ion is required to coagulate the colloid. These assumptions were later disproven by the work of Kruyt and Van Duin on As_2S_3 sol.

In case of non-electrolytes used here, it has been observed that the charge on the colloid continually increases. As the concentration of non-electrolytes used here is very low, so, the effect of interfacial tension is marked up to the concentration range studied, and hence, the charge goes on increasing by the increase in concentration of the non-electrolyte used. Whereas in the case of non-electrolytes used by Chatterji and Ramnath (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 2) the concentration of non-electrolytes used was high and hence the lowering of dielectric constant predominated and consequently the stability decreased.

It has been observed by Kruyt and Van Duin in the case of As_2S_3 sol that the effect of non-electrolytes e.g. phenol, on the precipitation value of electrolyte was determined by the nature of the precipitating ion; for univalent and trivalent ions the precipitation value was lowered, while with bivalent and tetravalent ions the precipitation value was raised. The precipitating ion used here is bivalent Ba. The results obtained are in confirmity with those of Van Duin and Kruyt.